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Original Article

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Comparison of Prognostic Scoring Systems in Patients with COVID-19 Pneumonia: The Role of PSI, CURB-65, DECAF, and PRIEST Scores in Predicting Mortality and Clinical Outcomes

ABSTRACT

Background: Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) has caused significant morbidity and mortality worldwide, highlighting the need for reliable prognostic tools to support clinical decision-making. Several scoring systems originally developed for community-acquired pneumonia and other respiratory diseases have been applied in COVID-19; however, their comparative effectiveness remains insufficiently clarified.

Methods: This retrospective observational study included 234 adult patients who presented to the Emergency Department of Ankara Training and Research Hospital between November 2020 and July 2021 with a diagnosis of COVID-19 pneumonia. Demographic characteristics, vital signs, comorbidities, laboratory results, and imaging findings were recorded. Four

prognostic scoring systems—the Pneumonia Severity Index (PSI), Confusion, Urea, Respiratory rate, Blood pressure–65 (CURB-65), Dyspnea, Eosinopenia, Consolidation, Acidemia, Atrial fibrillation (DECAF), and Pandemic Respiratory Infection Emergency System Triage (PRIEST)—were calculated. Clinical outcomes were categorized as discharge, ward admission, or intensive care unit admission, and 30-day mortality was assessed. Statistical analyses were performed using Kruskal-Wallis, Mann-Whitney U, chi-square, and ROC curve methods.

Results: Of the 234 patients, 108 (46.2%) were male and 126 (53.8%) were female, with a mean age of 61.5 years. Thirty-day mortality was identified in 42 patients (17.9%). Advanced age was significantly associated with mortality ($p < 0.05$). All four scoring systems demonstrated significant associations with both clinical outcomes and 30-day mortality. $PSI \geq 4$ predicted mortality with 88.1% sensitivity and 70% specificity (AUROC: 0.85), whereas $PRIEST \geq 13$ showed the best performance in predicting intensive care unit admission with 86.7% sensitivity and 87.9% specificity (AUROC: 0.93). For discharge, $PRIEST \leq 9$ provided the highest predictive accuracy (sensitivity: 94.8%, specificity: 69.3).

Conclusion: PSI, CURB-65, DECAF, and PRIEST scoring systems were all found to be significant in predicting mortality and clinical outcomes in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia. While PSI was the strongest predictor of mortality, PRIEST demonstrated superior predictive value for intensive care unit admission and discharge. Nevertheless, these scoring systems should be regarded as supportive tools rather than standalone decision-makers and should always be applied in conjunction with clinicians' judgment..

Keywords: COVID-19; Pneumonia; CURB-65; DECAF Score; Mortality

Introduction

Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), was first identified in December 2019 in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China. The disease can progress to severe pneumonia and respiratory failure, leading to life-threatening conditions (1). In March 2021, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared COVID-19 a global pandemic. Due to its rapid spread, the increasing number of cases caused significant disruptions in healthcare systems worldwide; shortages of healthcare personnel and personal protective equipment emerged, and health systems

were forced to adapt quickly to a state of critical overload (2).

According to WHO data, as of January 2022, the global number of confirmed COVID-19 cases had reached 305,914,000, while COVID-19-related deaths were reported as 5,486,000 (3). To reduce these high mortality rates, facilitate patient management, and accelerate clinical decision-making, prognostic scoring systems are considered valuable supportive tools.

The Pneumonia Severity Index (PSI), developed to facilitate the management of community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) patients, is a scoring system designed to predict 30-day adverse clinical outcomes—including the need for intensive care, mechanical ventilation, and mortality—based on age, vital signs, selected laboratory parameters, and radiological findings (4).

The Confusion, Urea, Respiratory Rate, Blood Pressure-65 (CURB-65) score was first developed in 2003 to accelerate and simplify the management of patients with community-acquired pneumonia (CAP). It is calculated based on mental status, serum urea level, vital signs, and age. Although originally designed for CAP, several studies have evaluated its applicability in patients with COVID-19 (5,6).

The Dyspnea, Eosinopenia, Consolidation, Acidemia, Atrial Fibrillation (DECAF) score

was developed to predict prognosis and facilitate management in acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (AECOPD). As AECOPD is often complicated by pneumonia, the CURB-65 score is frequently applied; however, DECAF was specifically designed to provide a more accurate prognostic assessment in patients hospitalized with AECOPD (7).

With the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic, the Pandemic Respiratory Infection Emergency System Triage (PRIEST) score was developed to enable rapid and effective management of patients with confirmed or suspected COVID-19. This score is calculated using age, vital signs, performance status, and sex (8).

The aim of this study was to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of four different scoring systems—PSI, CURB-65, DECAF, and PRIEST—in predicting prognosis among patients with COVID-19 pneumonia.

Materials And Methods

Study Design

This study was designed as a retrospective observational investigation. Following approval from the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Ankara Training and Research Hospital, Ministry of Health of Türkiye (Approval Code: E-93471371 dated 29.09.2021), medical records of adult

patients who presented to the Emergency Medicine Department of Ankara Training and Research Hospital, University of Health Sciences, between 1 November 2020 and 31 July 2021 were reviewed through the Hospital Information Management System (HIMS). Patients presenting to the emergency department with suspected COVID-19 and confirmed positive by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) testing were included in the study. The research was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the Good Clinical Practice (GCP) guidelines.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients presenting to the emergency department with suspected or confirmed COVID-19,
- Patients with a positive PCR test,
- Patients with chest imaging findings consistent with COVID-19 pneumonia,
- Patients aged over 18 years.

Exclusion criteria:

- Negative PCR test,
- Hospital admission due to non-COVID-19 causes (e.g., acute coronary syndrome, stroke, gastrointestinal bleeding),
- Absence of chest imaging findings,

- Missing laboratory or radiological data in the hospital information management system.

Data Collection Process

Cases registered in the hospital automation system within the specified time frame with ICD codes U07.3 (COVID-19) or Z03 (suspected diseases) were identified. Patient histories, physical examination findings, and consultation notes recorded during emergency department admissions were reviewed. Demographic data (age, sex), vital signs (blood pressure, heart rate, body temperature, respiratory rate, oxygen saturation), and comorbidities (asthma, COPD, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, chronic liver/renal disease, malignancy) were documented. PSI/PORT, CURB-65, DECAF, and PRIEST scores were calculated. Based on discharge summaries, patients were categorized into three groups: discharged, ward admission, and intensive care unit admission. Thirty-day mortality data were obtained by reviewing the hospital information management system records.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS for Windows, version 26.0. The normality of distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test for variables with $n \leq 50$ and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for variables with $n > 50$. Normally distributed numerical variables were presented as mean \pm standard

deviation, while non-normally distributed variables were expressed as median (min–max). The associations between the scoring systems and both discharge status and mortality were evaluated using the Kruskal-Wallis H and Mann-Whitney U tests. Cut-off values were determined by receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis, and sensitivity and specificity were calculated. The relationship between discharge and mortality was analyzed using the chi-square test, while the strength of the association was assessed with Phi and Cramer’s V analyses. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 816 patients were initially screened, of whom 582 were excluded due to meeting exclusion criteria. Specifically, 304 patients were excluded because of insufficient data in the hospital information system. Among the remaining patients, 178 were excluded due to negative COVID-19 PCR test results, leaving 334 patients. Of these, 18 patients lacked chest imaging findings and 21 showed no radiological evidence of pneumonia, and were therefore excluded. In addition, 4 patients were admitted with cerebrovascular events (CVE), 2 with acute myocardial infarction (AMI), and 1 with diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA), leading to their exclusion. Two patients presented after accidental ingestion

of eight chloroquine tablets and were excluded. Furthermore, 7 patients had no recorded blood samples, 16 had no documented performance status, and 29 had no electrocardiogram (ECG) available in the system, resulting in their exclusion. Ultimately, 234 patients met the inclusion criteria and were enrolled in the study. The flowchart of included and excluded patients is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Number of patients included and excluded in the study

Demographic Characteristics

Of the 234 patients included in the study, 108 (46.2%) were male and 126 (53.8%) were female, with ages ranging from 23 to 93 years. The mean age of all patients was 61.5 years. Demographic data are presented in Table 1, while the distribution of age according to clinical outcomes is shown in Table 2.

The mean age of patients discharged from the emergency department was 51.57 ± 2.03 years, those admitted to the ward had a mean age of 63.84 ± 1.32 years, and those admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) had

a mean age of 66.43 ± 1.70 years. Among comorbidities, the most common were hypertension (n=99), diabetes mellitus (n=68), and chronic heart disease (n=32), along with other systemic conditions.

Relationship Between Age, Clinical Outcomes, and Mortality

Age differed significantly among the groups of patients who were discharged, admitted to the ward, and admitted to the intensive care unit ($p < 0.05$). The lowest mean age was observed in the discharge group, whereas the highest mean age was found in the ICU admission group (Table 2). In addition, the mean age of survivors was 59.33 ± 15.02 years, while that of non-survivors was 71.83 ± 12.56 years, and this difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$; Table 3).

PSI/PORT Score

PSI scores differed significantly among the groups of patients who were discharged, admitted to the ward, and admitted to the intensive care unit ($p < 0.05$; Table 4). The highest PSI values were observed in the ICU admission group. A strong association was also found between PSI and mortality, with a median PSI of 132 in non-survivors compared to 77 in survivors ($p < 0.05$; Table 5, Figure 2).

Figure 2. Graphical representation of PSI/PORT scores according to mortality

CURB-65 Score

CURB-65 scores differed significantly among clinical outcome groups ($p < 0.05$; Table 6). The median CURB-65 score was 2.5 in the mortality group, whereas it was 1 in survivors ($p < 0.05$; Table 7, Figure 3).

Figure 3. Graphical representation of CURB-65 scores according to mortality

DECAF Score

The DECAF score showed significant differences among patients who were discharged, admitted to the ward, and admitted to the intensive care unit ($p < 0.05$; Table 8). The median DECAF score was 2.5 in non-survivors, compared with 2 in survivors ($p < 0.05$; Table 9, Figure 4).

Figure 4. Graphical representation of DECAF scores according to mortality

PRIEST Score

PRIEST scores also showed significant differences across clinical outcomes. The median score was highest in the intensive care unit group (15.5) and lowest in the discharge group ($p < 0.05$; Table 10). The median PRIEST score was 15 in the mortality group compared with 9 in survivors ($p < 0.05$; Table 11, Figure 5).

Figure 5. Graphical representation of PRIEST scores according to mortality

Clinical Outcomes, Mortality, and Comorbidity Relationship

Mortality was 3.4% among patients discharged from the emergency department, 12.9% among those admitted to the ward, and 41.7% in the intensive care unit group ($p < 0.05$; Table 12). Among patients with comorbidities, 32.7% were in the intensive care group, 11.5% were in the discharge group, and 55.8% were in the ward group. A statistically significant association was found between comorbidity and clinical outcomes ($p < 0.05$; Table 13).

Comparison of Scoring Systems

ROC analysis demonstrated that all scoring systems were statistically significant in predicting 30-day mortality. The PSI/PORT score, with a cut-off value of ≥ 4 , was identified as the strongest predictor of mortality, showing 88.1% sensitivity and 70% specificity (Table 14, Figure 6).

Figure 6. ROC curves of the four scoring systems according to 30-day mortality

For predicting intensive care unit admission, the PRIEST score performed best, with a cut-off value of ≥ 13 , demonstrating 86.7% sensitivity and 87.9% specificity (Table 15, Figure 7).

Figure 7. ROC curves of the four scoring systems according to intensive care unit admission

ROC analyses for ward admission did not yield significant cut-off values for any of the four scores (Table 16).

For discharge from the emergency department, the PRIEST score was found to be the most accurate, with a cut-off value of

≤ 9 , showing 94.8% sensitivity and 69.3% specificity (Table 17, Figures 8).

Figure 8. ROC curves of the four scoring systems according to discharge from the emergency department

Discussion

Since its emergence in December 2019, the COVID-19 pandemic has rapidly spread worldwide, with successive waves leading to a substantial increase in the demand for emergency department, ward, and intensive care unit beds, as well as diagnostic and therapeutic resources and healthcare workforce. This situation has been associated with a notable rise in both mortality and morbidity (2). To facilitate patient management, improve the accuracy of hospitalization decisions, and optimize resource utilization in order to reduce adverse outcomes, prognostic scoring systems are considered valuable tools in clinical practice (6).

In our study, a significant positive correlation was observed between the PSI score and 30-day mortality, with higher scores associated with increased mortality. Similarly, PSI scores were highest among

patients admitted to the ICU, lowest among those discharged, and intermediate in those admitted to the ward. ROC analysis revealed that a PSI cut-off value of ≥ 4 was the strongest predictor of mortality, with 88.1% sensitivity and 70% specificity.

Findings from the literature support our results. In a multicenter retrospective cohort study, Artero et al. reported that PSI and CURB-65 were superior to qSOFA and MuLBSTA in predicting mortality, with PSI showing greater prognostic value than CURB-65 (9). Similarly, in the study conducted by Anurag and Preetam, both PSI and CURB-65 were found to be significant in identifying critically ill patients; however, the SCAP score provided even stronger predictive accuracy (10). In our study, with the addition of the PRIEST score, PSI still emerged as the most effective predictor of mortality.

The CURB-65 score is a practical tool for clinicians due to its simple applicability. In our study, it was found to be significant in predicting both mortality and intensive care unit admission, with a cut-off value of ≥ 2 . Guo et al. reported that mortality increased significantly when CURB-65 was ≥ 2 (6). Similarly, in the study by Doğanay and Ak, CURB-65 was identified as a strong predictor of both mortality and ICU admission; however, the area under the

curve (AUC) values in our study were calculated to be lower (11).

Although originally developed for COPD exacerbations, the DECAF score was also found to be significant in predicting mortality and ICU admission in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia. In our study, a DECAF score ≥ 3 predicted mortality with 50% sensitivity and 85% specificity. Previous studies have also demonstrated that parameters such as eosinopenia, acidosis, and atrial fibrillation are associated with poor prognosis in COVID-19 (12–14).

The PRIEST score, developed specifically for COVID-19 during the pandemic, was identified in our study as the most effective system for predicting ICU admission. ROC analysis revealed that a cut-off value of ≥ 13 provided 86.7% sensitivity and 87.9% specificity. In the original study by Goodacre et al., the PRIEST score was also found to be a strong predictor of mortality and organ failure (8,15). These findings suggest that the PRIEST score may serve as a particularly effective tool for identifying critically ill patients.

In the broader literature, various biomarkers and scoring systems have been evaluated as prognostic indicators in COVID-19 pneumonia. For instance, in the study by Siber et al., presepsin levels were reported to be a significant predictor of mortality in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia (16),

supporting the notion that biomarkers may complement traditional scoring systems in prognostic assessment. Similarly, Erdem et al. demonstrated that the PSI score was reliable in determining which patients could be managed as outpatients, consistent with our finding that PSI was a strong predictor of mortality (17). Moreover, a recent study reported that a novel index, the Acute Phase Reactant Index (APhRI), which integrates inflammatory parameters, showed value in predicting mortality in pneumonia patients (18). These data suggest that, in addition to PSI, CURB-65, DECAF, and PRIEST, novel biomarkers and indices hold promise for improving the management of patients with COVID-19 pneumonia.

Overall, all four scoring systems evaluated in our study were statistically significant in predicting mortality and clinical outcomes in COVID-19 pneumonia. Each scoring system, however, demonstrated different strengths: PSI was the strongest predictor of mortality, PRIEST was most effective in predicting ICU admission, CURB-65 offered practical advantages in routine clinical use due to its simplicity, and DECAF was more limited but potentially useful in selected patient groups. Nevertheless, these scoring systems should not be used as stand-alone tools; rather, they must be applied in conjunction with clinical evaluation and physician judgment.

Limitations

In this study, 30-day mortality was evaluated based on hospital information system (HIMS) records, and patients who died within the first 30 days following hospital admission were included in the analysis according to their recorded date of death. However, in some cases, the exact cause of death could not be determined, which posed a limitation for mortality assessment. In addition, the laboratory parameters used in this study were obtained from the HIMS records and were accepted as accurate as recorded, which may carry a potential risk of bias related to laboratory measurements.

Conclusion

In our study, all of the evaluated scoring systems PSI/PORT, CURB-65, DECAF, and PRIEST were found to be significantly associated with 30-day mortality in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia and showed positive correlations with intensive care unit admission, ward admission, and discharge outcomes. While CURB-65 and DECAF stood out as practical tools due to their ease of use, PSI/PORT was the strongest predictor of mortality, and PRIEST demonstrated superior predictive value for ICU admission and discharge. Nevertheless, these scoring systems should not serve as sole determinants of clinical decisions; rather, they should be regarded as supportive tools that, when combined with physicians' clinical judgment, can enhance patient management.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics

Gender	n=234	Mean Age
Male	108 (%46.2)	63,1
Female	126 (%53.8)	62,2

Table 2. Age distribution according to clinical outcomes

Conclusion	Mean Age (Standard Deviation)	Significance
Discharge from the ED (n=58)	51,57± 2,03 (15,44)	p<0,05
Ward Admission (n=116)	63,84±1,32 (14,26)	p<0,05
Intensive Care Unit Admission (=58)	66,43±1,704 (12,97)	p<0,05

ED: Emergency Department

Table 3. Age distribution according to mortality

30-day Mortality	Mean Age (Standard Deviation)	Significance
Alive (n=192)	59,33 (15,02)	p<0,05
Deceased (n=42)	71,83 (12,56)	p<0,05

Table 4. Distribution of PSI scores according to discharge from the emergency department, ward admission, and intensive care unit admission

PSI	Median (Min-Max)	Significance
Discharge from the ED (n=58)	50 (15-159)	p<0,05
Ward Admission (n=116)	83 (36-190)	p<0,05
Intensive Care Unit Admission (n=60)	131 (67-248)	p<0,05

PSI: Pneumonia Severity Index, ED: Emergency Department

Table 5. Distribution of PSI scores according to mortality

Conclusion	Median (min-max)	Significane
Alive (n=190)	77 (15-217)	p< 0.05
Deceased (n=42)	132 (72-248)	p< 0.05

PSI: Pneumonia Severity Index

Table 6. Distribution of CURB-65 scores according to discharge from the emergency department, ward admission, and intensive care unit admission

Conclusion	Median (Min-Max)	Significance
Discharge from the ED (n=58)	0 (0-2)	p<0,05
Ward Admission (n=116)	1 (0-4)	p<0,05
Intensive Care Unit Admission(n=59)	3 (0-5)	p<0,05

ED: Emergency Department

Table 7. Distribution of CURB-65 scores according to mortality

Conclusion	Median (min-max)	Significance
Alive (n=190)	1 (0-4)	p< 0.05
Deceased (n=42)	2,5 (0-5)	p< 0.05

CURB-65: Confusion, Urea, Respiratory Rate, Blood Pressure, Age \geq 65 years

Table 8. Distribution of DECAF scores according to discharge from the emergency department, ward admission, and intensive care unit admission

Conclusion	Median (Min-Max)	Significance
Discharge from the ED (n=58)	1 (0-2)	p< 0.05
Ward Admission (n=116)	2 (0-3)	p< 0.05
ICU Admission(n=59)	3 (1-5)	p< 0.05

ED: Emergency Department, DECAF: Dyspnea, Eosinopenia, Consolidation, Acidemia, Atrial Fibrillation, ICU: Intensive Care Unit

Table 9. Distribution of DECAF scores according to mortality

Conclusion	Median (min-max)	Significance
Alive (n=190)	2 (0-5)	p< 0.05
Deceased (n=42)	2,5 (0-5)	p< 0.05

DECAF: Dyspnea, Eosinopenia, Consolidation, Acidemia, Atrial Fibrillation

Table 10. Distribution of PRIEST scores according to discharge from the emergency department, ward admission, and intensive care unit admission

Conclusion	Median (Min-Max)	Significance
Discharge from the ED (n=58)	4 (0-12)	p< 0.05
Ward Admission (n=116)	10 (3-20)	p< 0.05
ICU Admission (n=59)	15,5 (8-27)	p< 0.05

ICU: Intensive Care Unit, ED: Emergency Department, PRIEST: Pandemic Respiratory Infection Emergency System Triage

Table 11. Distribution of PRIEST scores according to mortality

Conclusion	Median (Min-Max)	Significance
Alive (n=190)	9 (0-20)	p< 0.05
Deceased (n=42)	15 (8-27)	p< 0.05

PRIEST: Pandemic Respiratory Infection Emergency System Triage

Table 12. Relationship between clinical outcomes and mortality

Conclusion	30-day Mortality		Significance
	Alive	Deceased	
Discharge from the ED (n=58)	56	2	p< 0.05
Ward Admission (n=116)	101	15	p< 0.05
ICU Admission (n=60)	35	25	p< 0.05

$\chi^2= 33,182$, ICU: Intensive Care Unit, ED: Emergency Department

Table 13. Relationship between comorbidity and clinical outcomes

Conclusion	Comorbidity		Significance
	Present	Absent	
Discharge from the ED (n=55)	18	37	p< 0.05
Ward Admission (n=115)	87	28	p< 0.05
ICU Admission (n=60)	51	9	p< 0.05

$\chi^2= 42,386$. ICU: Intensive Care Unit, ED: Emergency Department

Table 14. Summary table prepared by analyzing ROC curve and coordinates for 30-day mortality

	Cut-off	AUROC	Sensitivity	Specificity	
PSI/PORT	≥ 4	0,85 (0,80- 0,90)	88,1%	70%	p<0,05
CURB-65	≥ 2	0,80 (0,73- 0,87)	76%	68%	p<0,05
DECAF	≥ 3	0,71 (0,62- 0,8)	50%	85%	p<0,05
PRIEST	≥ 12	0,82 (0,76- 0,89)	78,5%	69,1%	p<0,05

ROC: Receiver Operating Characteristic, Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve, PRIEST: Pandemic Respiratory Infection Emergency System Triage, DECAF: Dyspnea, Eosinopenia, Consolidation, Acidemia, Atrial Fibrillation, CURB-65: Confusion, Urea, Respiratory Rate, Blood Pressure, Age ≥65 years

Table 15. Summary table prepared by analyzing ROC curve and coordinates for intensive care unit admission

	Cut-off	AUROC	Sensitivity	Specificity	
PSI/PORT	≥ 4	0,85 (0,80- 0,90)	81,7%	74%	p<0,05
CURB-65	≥ 2	0,85 (0,79- 0,90)	78%	74%	p<0,05
DECAF	≥ 3	0,87 (0,82- 0,92)	65%	94%	p<0,05
PRIEST	≥ 13	0,93 (0,89- 0,96)	86,7%	87,9%	p<0,05

ROC: Receiver Operating Characteristic, Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve, PRIEST: Pandemic Respiratory Infection Emergency System Triage, DECAF: Dyspnea, Eosinopenia, Consolidation, Acidemia, Atrial Fibrillation, CURB-65: Confusion, Urea, Respiratory Rate, Blood Pressure, Age ≥65 years

Table 16. Summary table prepared by analyzing ROC curve and coordinates for ward admission

	Cut-off	AUROC	Sensitivity	Specificity	
PSI/PORT	≥ 2	0,48 (0,40- 0,56)	93,1%	22,9%	p>0,05
CURB-65	≥ 1	0,46 (0,39- 0,54)	80%	35%	p>0,05
DECAF	≥ 3	0,48 (0,40- 0,56)	0,9%	67%	p>0,05
PRIEST	≥ 5	0,48 (0,40- 0,56)	95,7%	27,1%	p>0,05

ROC: Receiver Operating Characteristic, Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve, PRIEST: Pandemic Respiratory Infection Emergency System Triage, DECAF: Dyspnea, Eosinopenia, Consolidation, Acidemia, Atrial Fibrillation, CURB-65: Confusion, Urea, Respiratory Rate, Blood Pressure, Age ≥65 years

Table 17. Summary table prepared by analyzing ROC curve and coordinates for discharge from the emergency department

	Cut-off	AUROC	Sensitivity	Specificity	
PSI/PORT	≤ 2	0,83 (0,77- 0,89)	74,1%	78,4%	p<0,05
CURB-65	< 1	0,81 (0,75- 0,88)	69%	86,4%	p<0,05
DECAF	≤ 1	0,85 (0,80- 0,91)	86,2%	73,3%	p<0,05
PRIEST	≤ 9	0,91 (0,88- 0,95)	94,8%	69,3%	p<0,05

ROC: Receiver Operating Characteristic, Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve, PRIEST: Pandemic Respiratory Infection Emergency System Triage, DECAF: Dyspnea, Eosinopenia, Consolidation, Acidemia, Atrial Fibrillation, CURB-65: Confusion, Urea, Respiratory Rate, Blood Pressure, Age ≥65 years

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